

**ETHNOPHARMACOLOGICAL STUDY OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVE IN THE BLANAKAN
REGION, SUBANG, WEST JAVA, INDONESIA**

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ABSTRACT

All over the world cardiovascular diseases have remained one of the leading cause of death, hypertension (HT) being the most common and the main contributor to the pathogenesis of myocardial infarction, stroke and renal diseases. About 600 million patients suffer from hypertension as reports from WHO show that the incidence of hypertension exceeds more than 10% of the worldwide population. This research aims to document and preserve the use of ethnomedicine to treat HT by people in the Blanakan Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia. Fieldwork was carried out from November to December 2025 using direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature. The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system. Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org). This research reports that 30 plant species are commonly used by people in the Blanakan Region to treat HT. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (63.3%) are most often used in making medicine, followed by rhizome (13.3%), fruit (6.7%), flower (6.7%), stem, rind, and seeds (3.3% respectively). Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation methods were decoction (76.7%) and infusion (23.3%). The results of this research confirm that people in the Blanakan Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of HT with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

KEYWORDS: Traditional medicine, Ethnomedicinal plants, Blanakan Region, Hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

High blood pressure is a prevalent risk factor for cardiovascular disease. It affects over 72 million people in the United State and over 1 billion people worldwide.^[1,2] The burden of hypertension (HT) increases with age. Among individuals aged 60 and above, hypertension prevalence is 65.5%. Also, hypertension is associated with many chronic conditions such as insulin resistance, obesity, carbohydrate tolerance, concomitance, haemaglutinin, hyperuricacidemia, atherosclerosis and cardiovascular diseases.^[3] The Seventh Report of the Joint National

Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure (JNC7) recommends the blood pressure treatment goal of <140/90 mmHg for most patients and <130/80 mmHg for patients with diabetes mellitus (DM) or kidney disease.^[4] Also known as the "silent killer," hypertension is estimated to cause 4.5% of the current global disease burden and is as prevalent in many developing countries as in the developed world.^[3] Since the proportion of the hypertensive patients will increase dramatically worldwide, the prevention, detection, treatment and control of this condition should be a top priority.^[5]

However, most people in the developing countries have poor access to modern health care in using of the antihypertensive drugs and their combinations.

Antihypertensive drugs can be divided into six categories, including diuretic, β -blocking agents, calcium antagonists, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, angiotensin II receptor antagonists and α -receptor blocking agents.^[6] The efficacy of these drugs is only 40–60% and usually two or more antihypertensive drugs from different categories are needed to be combined to achieve the optimal results. However, side effects from these medications are an important concern.^[7] Recently, attention has been focused on herbal and mineral preparations that have been traditionally used in the prevention and management of cardiovascular diseases as the potential source for the new therapeutic agent development.^[3] In fact, medicinal plants are used to treat several diseases based on the folklore traditional wisdoms that have been perpetuated along several generations. It has been estimated that approximately 25% of all the prescribed medications today are of natural plant sources.^[8] Research to obtain new drugs to treat HT originating from natural ingredients continues to be carried out, one of which is through exploring active compounds from natural ingredients, especially medicinal plants which have traditionally been used by people to treat HT in various countries, especially Indonesia.^[9,10] One of the Region in Indonesia that still uses herbal plants as an alternative treatment, especially for treating HT, is Blanakan Region. This research aims to obtain detailed information about the use of herbal plants for alternative therapy for HT in Blanakan Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia using a field survey method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Blanakan is located in Subang Regency, West Java, Indonesia, with an area of 12.88 km². This area has an altitude of 25 meters above sea level with an average maximum air temperature of 33°C and a minimum of 24°C. Moreover, it is located between 06°15'47" South Latitude and 107°40'23" East Longitude. This region is a tropical climate area that is mostly inhabited by Sundanese tribes (95%) and other tribes (5%). Vegetation in the study area is in humid conditions with an average rainfall of 2,000 mm/year.

Data Collection

An extensive field survey was carried out to obtain information about medicinal plants from the Sundanese

tribe in the study area. To document existing information about medicinal plants from tribal practitioners, several field visits were conducted from November to December 2025 in the Blanakan Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia. During the research, ethnomedicinal information was collected from middle-aged and older tribal practitioners in their local language (Sundanese), through direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Information on local names of plants, plant parts used, preparation methods and administration routes (e.g., infusion, paste, juice and decoction) of all ethnomedicinal plants collected were recorded during the survey period.

Botanical Identification

Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature.^[11] The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system, except for Pteridophyta and Gymnospermae.^[12] Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org).

Ethics Statement

All participants provided verbal consent before the interview and gave consent to publish the information they provided.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research revealed that there are 30 plant species commonly used by the local Sundanese tribe to treat HT (Table 1). This shows that the study location is affordable in terms of biodiversity. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (63.3%) are most often used in making medicine, followed by rhizome (13.3%), fruit (6.7%), flower (6.7%), stem, rind, and seeds (3.3% respectively). The use of leaves is reported to be easier to prepare and easier to extract active substances from them for treatment. At the same time, leaves have less effect on the mother plant.^[13] Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation method was decoction (76.7%) and infusion (23.3%). These results are in line with previous research which reported that the forms of traditional medicine most widely used by the community were decoctions and infusions.^[11]

Table 1: Ethnomedicinal plants, local name, part used, mode of administration, and dosage uses in Blanakan, Subang, West Java, Indonesia.

No	Species	Family	Local name	Parts used	Mode of administration	Dosage of use
1	<i>Alpinia galanga</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Lengkuas	Rhizome	Decoction	25 grams once a day
2	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	Acanthaceae	Sambiloto	Leaf	Decoction	15 grams

	Nees					once a day
3	<i>Annona muricata</i> L.	Annonaceae	Sirsak	Leaf	Infusion	25 grams once a day
4	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Annonaceae	Srikaya	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
5	<i>Artocarpus altilis</i> (Park.) Forsberg	Moraceae	Sukun	Leaf	Decoction	80 grams once a day
6	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i> Lamk.	Moraceae	Nangka	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
7	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	Caricaceae	Pepaya	Flower	Decoction	25 grams once a day
8	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> J.Presl	Lauraceae	Kayu Manis	Stem	Decoction	50 grams once a day
9	<i>Cosmos caudatus</i> Kunth	Asteraceae	Kenikir	Leaf	Decoction	150 grams once a day
10	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kunyit	Rhizome	Infusion	200 grams once a day
11	<i>Etilingera elatior</i> (Jack) R.M.Sm.)	Zingiberaceae	Kecombrang	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
12	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> L.	Clusiaceae	Manggis	Rind	Infusion	100 grams once a day
13	<i>Gynura procumbens</i> (Lour.) Merr.	Asteraceae	Sambung Nyawa	Leaf	Infusion	50 grams once a day
14	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i> L.	Malvaceae	Rosela	Flower	Decoction	80 grams once a day
15	<i>Kaempferia galanga</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kencur	Rhizome	Infusion	100 grams once a day
16	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Anacardiaceae	Mangga	Leaf	Decoction	15 grams once a day
17	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Cucurbitaceae	Pare	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
18	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Mengkudu	Fruit	Infusion	20 grams once a day
19	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lamk.	Moringaceae	Kelor	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
20	<i>Nephelium lappaceum</i> L.	Sapindaceae	Rambutan	Leaf	Decoction	20 grams once a day
21	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Kemangi	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
22	<i>Phaleria macrocarpa</i> (Scheff.) Boerl)	Thymelaceae	Mahkota Dewa	Fruit	Decoction	40 grams once a day
23	<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae	Meniran	Leaf	Decoction	60 grams once a day
24	<i>Piper betle</i> L.	Piperaceae	Sirih	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
25	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i> L.	Asteraceae	Tempuyung	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
26	<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i> King.	Meliaceae	Mahoni	Seed	Decoction	5 grams once a day
27	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Myrtaceae	Jamblang	Leaf	Infusion	100 grams once a day
28	<i>Syzygium polyanthum</i> (Wight) Walpers	Myrtaceae	Salam	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
29	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i> Delile.	Asteraceae	Daun Afrika	Leaf	Decoction	5 grams once a day
30	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Rosc.	Zingiberaceae	Jahe	Rhizome	Decoction	150 grams once a day

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research confirm that people in the Blanakan Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of HT with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

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